

INTERVIEW GUIDE

GENERAL

Introduction

1. Interviewer introduces themselves
2. Explains the purpose of the research
3. Explains the structure of the interview

Demographics

The use of Digital Technology

1. What digital technology devices do you use?
2. How do you use those digital devices?
(examples: entertainment - YouTube, TikTok, source of information - FB, YouTube, Google, platform komunikasi - WA, dan lainnya).
3. What challenges do you face when using digital devices?

Searching for information

1. From which sources do you obtain information?
 - a. Why do you choose those sources?
2. What challenges/obstacles do you face when searching for information?
3. What type of information presentation do you prefer? (text, video, infographic, audio)
 - a. Why do you prefer those presentations?

Information and Agriculture Apps

1. From which sources do you obtain agricultural information?
 - a. Why do you choose those sources?
2. What challenges/obstacles do you face when searching for agricultural information?
 - a. In which area do you face challenges? (financial, skills, lack of information, access to information sources)
3. During which stage of farming does agricultural information help you the most? (planting, mid-season, harvest)
 - a. What type of information do you usually look for?
 - b. From which sources do you obtain that information?
 - c. Why do you choose those sources?
4. Do you use any digital agriculture applications?

- a. (If yes)
 - i. Which application do you use?
 - ii. To what extent has the application been helpful?
 - iii. What do you like from those applications?
 - iv. What do you think needs to be improved in the application?
 - b. (If no) Why don't you use any digital agriculture applications?
5. Do you think digital agricultural applications can help with farming activities and obtaining/sharing agricultural information?
 - a. How can such applications help you?